

Buried grating fabrication process for 7xx nm DFB laser diodes

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In this study we present improvements of the buried grating fabrication process for edge emitting distributed feedback (DFB) lasers in the 760 to 795 nm wavelength range. DFB lasers are compact, narrow-band light sources supporting a wide range of photonic applications.

Our standard process starts with the first metalorganic vapour-phase epitaxy (MOVPE) growth that has GaAs/ InGaP/ GaAsP grating layers (thicknesses 10/ 13/ 20 nm) on top of a 90 nm thick InGaP layer. This layer covers the underlying AlGaAs cladding and protects it from unwanted oxide formation. Grating lines with a period of about 230 nm and a width of 80 nm are patterned into a negative electron beam (e-beam) ma-N 2401 resist followed by three selective wet-chemical etch steps, resist removal with NMP and extensive cleaning (Fig. 1). Subsequently, the second epitaxial growth completes the vertical laser structure. For the described process we experience a small process window making it critical to maintain stable DFB laser performances. We therefore studied a different process with 100 nm thick HSQ resist (EM Resist LTD), again patterned with e-beam lithography, followed by a 50 nm deep dry-etch and removal of the HSQ with hydrofluoric acid (HF). The wafer surfaces from this process show low roughness after MOVPE overgrowth indicating a low defect density of the vertical laser structure (Fig. 2). These findings are confirmed with cross-section SEM images on cleaved samples and on lamella prepared with FIB (Fig. 3). Although the process flow with HSQ is well suited for the buried grating fabrication process, the resist is comparatively slow with dose values 4 to 5 times higher than for the ma-N 2401 resist, resulting in a total exposure time longer than a day for our three-inch wafer DFB standard layout. However, other lithographic grating patterning methods cannot provide the flexibility of e-beam lithography needed for our broad portfolio of device designs [1]. Therefore, we studied the writing times of a layout which contains approximately 3300 DFB lasers on a three-inch wafer and around 5 % of the wafer area has to be exposed for grating definition (dimension of chips $1500 \times 400 \mu\text{m}^2$ and of grating fields $1480 \times 70 \mu\text{m}^2$). After optimizing the exposure scheme with data preparation software on modern e-beam systems (Raith EBPG5200 and Vistec SB251) we ended up with about 12 hours per wafer writing time, which is adequate for our process requirements.

Fig. 4 shows measurement results from a DFB laser, that was fabricated with the analyzed process flow. The 1500 μm long device with a 2.2 μm wide ridge waveguide was facet coated (reflectivity of 0 % and 96 % for the front and rear facet, respectively) and mounted on C-mount. While we significantly simplified the process, the measurements results are comparable to DFB laser performances earlier published [2]. Further results will be presented on the MNE2024 conference.

[1] H. Virtanen, T. Uusitalo, M. Karjalainen, S. Ranta, J. Viheriälä and M. Dumitrescu "Narrow-Linewidth 780-nm DFB Lasers Fabricated Using Nanoimprint Lithography," IEEE Photonics Technology Letters, vol. 30, no. 1 (2018), DOI 10.1109/LPT.2017.2772337

[2] O. Brox, F. Bugge, A. Mogilatenko, E. Luvsandamdin, A. Wicht, H. Wenzel and G. Erbert "Distributed feedback lasers in the 760 to 810 nm range and epitaxial grating design" Semicond. Sci. Technol., vol. 29, no. 095018 (2014), DOI 10.1088/0268-1242/29/9/095018

Fig. 1 Buried grating fabrication process flows

Fig. 2 HSQ grating lines before RIE (top) and DFB wafer surface after 2nd epitaxy, waveguide etch and SiN_x isolation layer (bottom)

Fig. 3 XS-SEM (BSE) of a cleaved sample in the wafer analytic field (bottom) and HAADF-SEM of a FIB lamella in the 2.2 μm wide DFB-RW (top)

Fig. 4 Optical spectra at pump currents of 50 mA to 150 mA (bottom) and light-current-voltage characteristics of a DFB fabricated with the analysed process flow (top)